

THE ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AND JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE AND BEHAVIORAL CHANGES: A QUALITATIVE CASE STUDY AT ONE PUBLIC JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN JAMBI CITY

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the effects of teaching Environmental Education (EE) to youth and how teaching EE reflects long term appreciation for environmental awareness. More specifically, it aimed to explore students' knowledge, attitudes, and actions towards environmental lifestyle as part of Adiwiyata program. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and they were audio taped, transcribed, and carefully analyzed. The study was designed as a qualitative design with a case study approach, and involved five teachers and nine students outdoor activities; based on curriculum and related to students' daily behavior as the result of environmental education. Indeed, the finding of the study revealed four major themes concerned on the effect of the environmental education regarding to Adiwiyata program; recognizing recycled goods, safeguarding the environment and cleanliness, building awareness to pro environmental action, and fostering awareness to loving plants.

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1.Introduction

The idea of this research project emerged from the discussions during one of the classes in the master's program in educational management. We were concerned about current environmental challenges that Indonesia is facing. Questions and worries raised during our discussions and led into consideration of changing young generation's ecological behavior because human environmental conditions decreased from year to year caused by human activities to meet their needs. As a result, human faces environmental degradation and problems. Some issues on climate change, the decline of ecosystems, the depletion of the ozone layer, rapid population growth, forest degradation, increasing urbanization, acid rain, declining biodiversity species and natural habitats, as well as pollution (IGES, 2001). Some efforts have to be done to reduce or stop the environmental degradation and problems through a sustainable development strategy that can be integrated with the educational system at all levels, lines, and other types of education as education is the key agent of change in the context of implementation. For that purpose, the United Nations has proclaimed 2005-2014 the —"Decade of Education for Sustainable Development with the overall goal of —integrating the principals, values, and practices of sustainable development into all aspects of education and learning" [UNESCO, 2005, p.1].

Regarding the United Nations' Education for Sustainable Development, Indonesia has not specified an explicit commitment to the Environmental Education (EE) program to teach the next generation about sustainable practices. However, in elementary and secondary schools, the Environmental Education (EE) is rooted in the subjects such as Science and geography. Also, the national education dedicates to all aspects of national development, especially the development of human resources corresponding to the demands of development in the context of globalization. Additionally, some classes at specific schools describe themselves as "sustainable" in either syllabi or course descriptions and each of these schools has a long-standing reputation as a green school.

The importance of Environmental Education has become concerns by some authors such as Stepp, Bennett, and Bryan [1969, p. 30] who defined, "Environmental education is aimed at producing a citizenry that is knowledgeable concerning the biophysical environment and its associated problems, aware of how to help solve these problems, and motivated to work towards their solution." Additionally, international definition was adopted by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization [UNESCO, 1975, p. 10], "The goal of environmental education is to develop a world population that is aware of, and concerned about, the environment and its associated problems, and which has the knowledge, skills, attitudes, motivations, and commitment to work individually and collectively toward solutions of current problems and the prevention of new one." According to Clayton and Myers [2009], three main aspects involve in environmental education goals, namely cognition, affect, and behavior. In terms of the cognitive aspect, it includes knowledge of ecology and awareness of environmental problems. For the affective aspect, it includes motivation to change, emotional attachment, and feeling that "one can make a difference and commitment to continue one's effort" [Clayton & Myers, 2009, p.182]. In terms of Behavior aspect, it includes green consumerism, pro-environmental policy support, citizenship behaviors, activism, land management choices, collective actions and so forth.

In relation with the United Nations' Education for Sustainable Development and the importance of Environmental Education as Clayton and Myers [2009] discussed above, however, in Indonesian context, Environmental Education has not become an integral part of school curriculum. This situation may lead children not to grow up as socially and environmentally responsible citizens although children's environmental values and attitude might be affected by their surrounding society, especially by the closest family members. However, one of the junior high schools in Jambi focused of this study has claimed as a –go-green school. In order to see the broader view of how environmental education works in this school, in particular, what effects of environmental education through *Adiwiyata Program* has on students by looking at their knowledge, attitude and actions towards environmental lifestyle.

2 Purpose and Significance

The purpose of this study was to find out the effects environmental education through *Adiwiyata Program* that the students have by looking at their knowledges and behavioral changes towards environmental lifestyle. Under these circumstances, based on a fieldwork, this thesis attempts to deepen the current

knowledge of environmental education in schools. The information gathered in this paper might be useful for scholars interested in similar research due to very few previous studies written in English about environmental education in Indonesia.

3.Methods

In this research, a qualitative design with a case study approach was used to explore students' knowledge, attitude and actions towards environmental lifestyle as part of Adiwiyata Program.

In selecting participant, we purposefully planned to recruit all the last years' students and all teachers and to get access. In this study, a purposeful sampling with a convenience case strategy was used in which researcher can access and easily collect data [Creswell, 2007]. Furthermore, a semi- structured interview was conducted individually with each student and teacher based on their availability and location of the teacher chose.

In analyzing the data, all the transcripts among participants analyzed and compared to search similarities and differences. The transcripts were reread line-by-line in order to find regularities and emerging themes and subthemes among the data. Once all the interview data coded and analyzed, we started to identify how themes and sub-themes help me to explain our research question. During this process, we removed or reduced overlapping and repetitive data. However, to establish the "trustworthiness" [Lincoln & Guba 1985, p. 300] or to verify the accuracy of data, findings, and interpretations [Creswell, 1998], the researcher completed the following procedures. First, this research undertook prolonged engagement and repeated interviews [Creswell, 1998 & Merriam, 1998]. Second, we triangulated data through multiple interviews. Triangulation is "a procedure using multiple sources of data to see whether they converge to provide evidence for validating interpretations of results" [Perry, 2005, p. 251]. Third, member checks were used in order to get participant feedback on the accuracy and credibility of the data, findings, interpretations, and conclusions.

4. Findings and Discussion

The Program and Its School

Adiwiyata is a program of the school that embodies insightful and caring environment. It means a good place and ideal which can be obtained all the science and norms and ethics that can be the basis for the creation of human well-being and toward the ideals of sustainable development. According to the interview data reported by the head of Adiwiyata program, there are four major steps in realizing Adiwiyata School presented in the following table.

Table 1. Four Major Steps in Realizing Adiwiyata School

Steps	Subject Matter
1. Policies that favor and embodied in the form of vision and mission	Vision contains implementation (taqwa, cultured, superior, and environmental and global) - The vision embodied in the form of a mission related to the environment Plans put in the form of school work plan - Schools should commit to provide a minimum of 20% of the budget
2. Making education the curriculum of environmental	Three models: integrated, specialized specific subjects, combinations Curriculum (document 1): curriculum load, vision, mission Curriculum (document 2): syllabus, lesson plan - 5 minutes clean Recommendation - Project learning
3. Participatory activities	- Garbage tickets - Sasisapo - Sagusapo - Saturday clean - Making fertilizer - A narrow land use - Cooperation (WARSI, Bank 9) - Inviting business industry - Daily picket
4. Setting up the infrastructure	

The Effect of Environmental Education on Knowledge and Behavioral Changes of Students

The main activity of Adiwiyata program is to realize institutional school with care and cultured environment for elementary and secondary school levels in Indonesia. Adiwiyata program is expected to change the mindset of young generations (students) to the importance of environmental balance. The concept of environmental balance, then likely to be generated candidates leaders who understand and implement the concept of sustainable development. There are four major topics regarding the effect of Adiwiyata program through environmental education presented as follow.

Table 6. The effect of environmental education for students

Theme	Sub- theme
Recognizing recycled goods	-
Safeguard the environment and cleanliness	-
Building awareness for pro-environmental action	-
Fostering awareness to loving plants	-

Recycling has an idea as the process of turning scrap materials or waste into new materials that can be reused. With the recycling process, the garbage can be something useful to reduce the use of new raw materials. Another benefit is to save energy, reduce pollution, reduce land degradation and greenhouse gas emissions in the process of new goods maker. For the first theme, a male student expressed that she can recognize what goods that can be recycled as the effect getting from environmental education, he comments:

“...berguna.. jadi kita bisa tau mana yang bisa didaur ulang, barang yang sebenarnya tidak berguna bisa berguna lagi.” (Ariel)

“: terus tidak ada sampah yang menumpuk yang mencemari lingkungan.” (Ariel)

The most importantly, everyone can participate in the recycling process. At least two the initial process of recycling; collecting and sorting trash that can be done at any time.

Safeguard the Environment and Cleanliness

Environmental hygiene is inseparable from human life and as a fundamental element in prevention and health sciences. What is meant by the cleanliness of the environment is to create a healthy environment that is not prone to various diseases such as dengue fever, vomiting and others. This can be achieved by creating an environment clean beautiful and comfortable. Responding to the second theme, two students conveyed their true feelings as the effect with regard to environmental education. They state:

“kalo dipelajari itu berguna sekali untuk masa depan karena...aaa...karena itu bisa membantu diri kita sendiri pribadi untuk selalu menjaga lingkungan dan kebersihan.” (Yolan)

“materi tentang lingkungan ini sangat berguna karena mengajarkan diri kita sendiri untuk senantiasa membersihkan lingkungan dan diri sendiri karena kebersihan itu sebagian daripada iman.” (Yamin)

According to statements above, the students emphasized on safeguarding the environment and cleanliness as the effect of environmental education that they get from school.

Building Awareness for Pro-environmental Action

Pro- environmental or green behavior is how human beings do good and avoid bad deeds in the neighborhood. Its role related to sustainable development being implemented in various countries including Indonesia, as it seeks to meet the needs of the present without compromising the right to meet the needs of future generations by minimizing environmental damage as much as possible and able to use the environment wisely. Being asked regarding to this theme, a student says:

“pendidikan lingkungan itu pastinya sangat berguna kesuksesan itu juga dari kesadaran kita terhadap lingkungan dan itu sangat berguna karena...karena lingkungan itu ...aaa...harus selalu dijaga supaya tidak rusak.” (Stefy)

However, as we know, to realize the environmental awareness in school at this time is still difficult performing well although it has been attempted with the ability as maximally as possible by providing adequate sanitation facilities around the school, and making school regulation that support as a control means of control.

Fostering Awareness to Loving Plants

Article II. Loving the earth does not have the grandiose activities. It is enough with loving plants and reforest the earth back. Maintain plants around is a real form of loving earth. With regard to this theme, a female student conveys:

“tapi yang untuk..yang paling berpengaruh itu yang tadi, yang Jambore Sanitasi, itu membuat saya memupuk kebiasaan ngingati kawan gitu atau jadi lebih suka nanam-nanam lagi, lalu....” (Stefy)

Overall, to reach Adiwiyata school cultured and environment, there are several steps that must be prepared involving the various stakeholders, both from the government level and the school or the community around the school.

New pro-environmental habits accepted from Environmental Learning

Findings of this study showed that the individual behavior cannot be directly predicted and explained by the individual’s environmental attitudes formulated in light of environmental knowledge. Therefore, I tried to explore the new pro- environmental habits accepted from environmental education. As showed in the following table, I found four salient themes concerned on new pro- environmental habits (behaviors); Participate in activities of mutual cooperation, accustomed to sort trash, disposing trash in its place, and exemplifying good habits.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to explore students' knowledge, attitude and actions towards environmental lifestyle as part of a –go-green school. To do that, research questions were addressed that related to the effect of environmental education through a –go-green school that the students have by looking at their knowledge, attitudes and actions towards environmental lifestyle. This chapter discusses the results of this study, as well as possibilities for future research.

The Aim of Environmental Education

In Indonesia, environmental educators, both formal and informal, have been trying to establish environmental education as a discipline to be taught in schools from primary to secondary levels. The need to develop education programs that enable students and citizens to acquire a universal environmental ethic has been recognized both nationally and internationally (Engleson & Yockers, 1994). Indeed, the goal of environmental education in the current school is to help students become environmentally aware, knowledgeable, skilled, and dedicated citizens who are committed to work individually and collectively to defend, improve, and sustain the quality of the environment on behalf of present and future generations of all living things is very consistent with Engleson and Yockers [1994] defined.

Discussion of the Impacts on Students

The perceived impacts on skills such as thinking and life skills were still rated as being, while not as highly as the impacts on attitudes. The skills such as recycling helped develop their thinking skills. Thinking is able to take concepts out of books and relate them to real life issues that the students are able to identify with. For example, when students studied environmental issues, it made more of an impact on the students to bring it in real life situations that hit close to home. It allows the students to associate environmental problems and solutions with things going on in their backyard.

As noted earlier in this paper, encouraging these discrete behaviors, such as recycling when away have value on their own merit, but can be employed as part of a broader plan to develop a deeper environmental coconsciousness across behavioral domains. Individuals who engage in conservation behaviors are more likely to engage in similar behaviors in the future due the principle of justification of effort [Cialdini & Goldstein, 2004]

Indeed, as well as the following items, many of which are commonly used to indicate global pro-environmental behavior in survey based, correlational studies: recycling and making handicraft (products) made of recycled materials, , and purchasing organic foods [Gutierrez, 1996].

In terms of methods, the finding based on teachers' perspectives, direct practice (experiential) as one of methods is strongly supported by Carlson et al, [2011] and Dewey [cited in Kochlar, 1992]. They wrote that many writers who agreed that the best practice for environmental education is by field experience, as one of the informal education about the environment, children should learning through activities. Learning from experience or learning by doing [Gandhi, Kilpatrick & Dewey, cited in Kochhar, 1992] recommended today and is defined as the process of reaching understanding, knowledge, skills, and attitudes through

practical and applied activities [Kostova & Atasoy, 2008]. In addition, student perceived toward environmentally influenced their interest in environmentally friendly behavior (Cheng & Monroe, 2010). It could be seen from four themes found in the findings from effect of environmental education for the students. Regarding to the setting of outdoor activity such planting in the garden, the finding of this study revealed that the outdoor activities reduced symptoms significantly when compared to the other settings [Kuo & Taylor, 2004]. However, Fishman [2005] conducted a study similar to this particular research; however she focused specifically on an urban environmental education program. She wanted to research how the awareness of children on their biophysical environment would be impacted by this type of programming. Fishman [2005] noted that, awareness is a relevant variable to consider when assessing the impact of a place-based environmental education program on elementary school students. She also stated that the word awareness can have broad interpretations and that the researcher must distinguish what they mean when using the word. In constructing this study, we decided to focus on the students's knowledge and behavioral changes on environmental education. As a result, Fishman's study showed that students living in high socioeconomic neighborhoods presented with local environmental awareness in comparison to those of lower socioeconomic standings. This situation seems like what we found, students living in high socioeconomic neighborhoods, they used to tell his assistants in doing things related to hygiene, particularly in the Area home. For example, such as taking out the trash, they mostly do not really care throwing it in a place that has been provided, or perhaps sorting organic and inorganic waste.

5. Conclusion

Schools could potentially be the place to build awareness of environment conservation efforts. They have a great social responsibility to form individuals who always favor the environment. More and more caring schools and cultured environment means, in the future, the more nation's children have the responsibility of maintaining environmental conservation.

Adiwiyata school model is not just a green school, while the important thing is how to change the behavior of the school community. For example, the usual littering and letting piled everywhere changed fond sort and recycle the garbage. Regular school let land lay overgrown bushes, became interested in cultivating. with production plants, ornamental plants, and herb, which usually extravagant in consumption of natural resources and energy, started to make efficiency by saving resources. Schools with Adiwiyata program is expected to create learning situations which seemed to blend with nature. Unless it through the program, the school researched the potential to give rise culture of student oriented. A culture oriented utilizing nature as a learning resource, the object of research, and interpret it from different angles. Culture is expected to build a framework. They think children of various dimensions through the natural research process. Developing curriculum-based environment, becoming an important aspect of encouraging schools Adiwiyata models. The mechanism, by integrating environmental material cross subjects and subjects or be a stand-alone local content. SBC developed a decentralized potentially adapting environmental education become a stand-alone subject. There are several suggested improvement needed by the school (administrators, teachers, the head of Adiwiyata program, students,

and staff). First, accumulating research regarding the influences of behavior on attitudes, and regarding the effectiveness of behaviorist approaches in influencing behavior, suggests that there is a need to reassess the status of achieving behavioral change as an ultimate goal of environmental education and to reconsider the status of attitude development as an environmental education goal. Second, the school is not really successful in influencing parents' behavior. The theory of social constructivism can provide some explanations for these findings. According to the theory, attitudes are socially constructed, and people need to be involved in their learning processes. Third, in terms of enthusiastic schools/ head of Adiwiyata program to Implement Adiwiyata, in the implementation of this program, it is required a high willingness of the Head of Adiwiyata program. Head of Adiwiyata program task is to find funding or budget for running Adiwiyata program and oversee the passage of the program. The head of Adiwiyata program motivates community to run this program then gives awards to community who have successfully run the program, so that people given the award will become more enthusiastic and motivating other people to get the award as well. Fourth, with regard to teachers and head of Adiwiyata program training. In order to provide program managers in the field, it is necessary once implemented training for head of Adiwiyata program and teachers to equip the knowledge and skills implemntasi environmental education in schools. Training teachers and head of Adiwiyata programs implemented in three stages, namely the first year to provide training on the concept of environmental education, school environmental programs and activities that should be implemented. In the first year of activities that should be implemented is stage 1 to stage 4 in the figure). In the second year of training on the integration of environmental education into the curriculum, and the third year of training in partnership with the community outside of school.

6. Recommendation for Further Research

This study can be used as a resource for future research within environmental education field. I would recommend to focus research on younger or older age groups. In this study I found that all my significant results reside within one of secondary schools group and none within the older middle school group. I would also recommend a much larger sample size. Results were limited based on the studies extremely small sample sizes. Analyses of significant became more difficult with a bigger sample size. One area that could use closer examination would be to do a comparative study with varying backgrounds (rural, suburban, and urban). The study could observe the similarities and differences in the students' perception of environmental education and environmental awareness.

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